

Digitalization in educational systems. Teaching art in the age of computer technology

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Abstract

The rapid pace of societal change and the proliferation of new technologies are changing practically every area of our personal and professional lives, including how we work, think, play, communicate, send, and disseminate information. Use of technology in education has an impact on teacher-student interaction. Innovation is a global paradigm shift in each aspect of our society, including the community of education, transforming itself and its functioning. With the development of modern technology, the process of teaching art is changing. Over the last decade, computers have begun to play another role in the great benefits of art education. Images in an electronic format can no longer be separated from the basic composition of art education. Electronic media has changed the way

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art is taught, students learning about art, and ultimately the way art teachers understand art lessons. The relationship that has been established between art and computer technology is critical in defining the future of the educational system. Throughout history, the worlds of art and art education have employed technology in their processes. Art teachers are now responsible for teaching not only traditional subjects but also image processing technologies. Crucial to future teaching is how teachers will integrate and combine traditional teaching tools, processes, and ways of thinking about Art with the new tools, new processes and thinking skills needed to blend and utilize the complex variety of information concepts in today's world. This paper elaborates how computer and related technologies can be applied in teaching art, the extent of impact that computer-assisted art has on art students and the utilization of technology to ameliorate the teaching of strategies of thinking and learning and the development of art-centered cognitive skills.

Keywords: *technology, computer, art, school, teaching, teacher*

1. Introduction

The rapid pace of societal change and the proliferation of new technologies are impacting practically every area of our personal and professional lives, including how we work, think, play, communicate, send, and disseminate information. During World War II, the computer was invented at the same time as television, and it was employed as an electronic device for storing and processing data. Until the 1960s, computer development was distinct from the one of the televisions. Given that the capabilities and functions of the computer and television were almost the same, technology became increasingly sophisticated and experimental in a short period of time. Computer imaging is a new field of study that combines computer image and television innovation. It became evident that television, computer imaging, image processing, and transmission had a unique interaction.

With the advent of new technologies, the relationship between computer imaging and television became less divergent, allowing the digital format to become the conventional pre-electronic image. In this regard, it made it possible for the very first-time mathematics, a universal language, to lay the foundations for the use of technologies for the image interface.

With the development of digital technology, the role of the computer increased in terms of synthesizing and storing images for visual images. The computer became the primary device for electronic media as technology advanced, thus playing a

greater role in creating, inventing, processing, sorting, combining, analyzing, improving, and modifying images. On the other hand, the computer could retrieve images from a variety of sources, including video, still photos, electronic images, and drawings. Computer skills were expanded by other communication possibilities in the network, such as the Internet, social media, etc.

Technology in education has influenced the way teachers and students interact in learning. Technological innovations have brought about radical changes in each aspect of today's society, including the community of education, bringing about transformations in our daily family, professional and economic lives. The use of the computer also took off in education, where it plays an extremely important role. The computer is used to receive, process, deliver, and disseminate information and to serve as a tool that can be utilized for teaching as well as learning.

2. Reform of technology in teaching art

With the advancement of modern technologies, the art teaching technique will alter as well. In the last ten years, the computer has taken on a new role that benefits art instruction greatly. The essential foundations of creative education can no longer be separated from electronic image. The way art is taught has altered because of electronic and digital technologies. Students gain knowledge of art and how art teachers view art education. Computers also alter the process and technique of making images in every sector in which art student's work, including printing, design, painting, and sketching.

There are three important reasons underpinning cultural change for the inclusion of computer information technology (CIT) and art of media in programs and curricula of Art. The first reason is that visual symbols, iconography, and the sophisticated communication system are becoming increasingly important around the world. The expanding importance of technology-related aesthetic judgements, at the individual level and cultural level, is the second reason for including technology in teaching. The third reason has to do with the increasing social necessity for connectivity, or the recognition of different forms of social interaction.

To develop curricula, the main basis of any process of art instruction should be the ability to treat, utilize and renovate different artistic systems, to ruminate and build with the ingredients of an artistic medium. If this medium is the computer, its use means the regular application, processing and acquisition of its qualities and advantages for artistic products. The use of computer in teaching makes it necessary to analyze the processes of computer operation and the expectations that arise to create symbols. Artistic learning is closely related to the search for computer learning.

Furthermore, the production, perception, and reflection competences should be the substance of art curriculum. In this way the connection of art education with computer technology can be strengthened. The Ministry of Education in Albania is reviewing the artistic curriculum to ensure the combination of arts and crafts in the pre-university system. With the completion of the artistic curriculum review process, it is expected that the combined use of teaching art and technology will further ameliorate the quality of both teaching and learning, viewed also from the standpoint of meeting the market needs for “computerized” artists.

The partnership established between art and information technology is extremely important in determining the prospects of education. The domain of art and its education has embraced technology in the very first steps of the latter. A substantiated argument for the necessity of intertwining innovative technologies with old-style forms of art emerges when we address the strengthening of the connection of the old with the new. Important perceptions will be developed in the process of connecting technology with new tradition. We need to convince that the computer will never replace art studios. Rather, computers and art studios will work side by side to the benefit of students. They have the advantage of cooperation and combination, but without harming one other. It would do great harm to education if teachers emphasized one aspect and just overlooked the other. The use of the computer in education of art will not need to substitute existing methodologies but should rather be an additional form of creative process employed in classes or art curriculum.

Introducing technology to teaching art calls for teachers to review the substance of art curricula. A new model of artistic education is suggested that incorporates new imaging and sound technology and should be introduced to students to provide them with the skills required in today’s world. In this context, it would be appropriate to enrich the content more with computer images in the well-known fields of art history, criticism, aesthetics, perspective and content in future art education curricula. Let us take as an example history of art: integrating new technology into traditional programs of art education. It is quite clear that the history of art becomes very fascinating and most effective in almost every study embarked on with different media, but that is unlike the practice of conventional teaching of history of art in the fact that increasing the amount of information is a constant need in every class.

The use of computer in the art curriculum makes it necessary to better understand the curriculum’s objectives and purposes and that the use of the computer to create artworks should not underestimate the principles, notions and practice or methods of art. According to Greh (1990), computers should be employed as a medium in art classes, and the generated images should undergo critical deliberations and study.

Art teachers will need to carry out the duty of teaching not only in conventional areas of study but in image technology as well. It is important for the future of education that teachers integrate the traditional art tools, processes and thinking into the new tools and processes and into thinking skills that are required to synthesize the complex variety of information concepts in today's world.

Technology makes learning fun. Identifying ways to make learning more fun is of crucial importance for the quality of learning. New forms of exchanging information, encouraging collaboration among students and promoting the skills required in century 21 not only can be useful for developing critical thinking, communication, creativity and collaboration, but can also be fun and engaging for students and teachers themselves.

Technology offers a variety of opportunities to integrate formation assessments. Assessment in the art class can be tedious dependent on attendance by the students in the class, especially in those schools where the number of students per class is large. Technology can help facilitate this process by providing a variety of forms of easy and effective teaching to assess as realistically as possible the knowledge gained by students using computer-based assessment applications systems.

Technology also boosts and promotes engagement. A major concern in the classroom is students' engagement and involvement. If we want students to be seriously involved in the class, the learning activities must be interactive. Technology is a great way to get students engaged and interested in the subject matter. Whether the lesson is taught simply using a PowerPoint presentation of famous artworks or by playing a video from the life and work of great painters, both forms can easily grab students' attention. These computer-based forms of interactive learning foster student engagement.

As far as university art students are concerned, not only has it become unquestionable for them to be skilled in computer image processing, but it has already become a requirement for admittance into practically any discipline of visual arts research and study. (Brunner & Tally, 1999). All domains of art call for technical knowhow and basic competencies in computer processing imaging. Those students who lack these skills are at a huge disadvantage compared to other students. Painters, sculptors, and artists are using computer in various forms, both in the artistic process, in their scientific and artistic research as well as to run their art businesses. The requirement for the possession of information technology knowhow is indispensable for every visual arts student. Students should be instructed in the use of visuals and technology, similarly to their learning and teaching in art studio, esthetics, history of art, and critique of art.

3. Applications of computer in education of art

With the introduction of technology into the world of teaching art, computers have already become an instrument for creating and enhancing the image for teachers of visual art. By nature, a computer can act as a communication medium to be made use of, which can foster collaboration with any other medium dynamically.

Moreover, there are now many applications that allow computers to help students simulate old-style means, by offering textures, processing images, and enabling numerous digital collages. Considering such a system, students do not need additional materials. Even the completed image can be stored and inspected on a computer. However, we must keep in mind that here the computer is not doing the job for the student in a direct manner but is offering electronic alternatives and options of traditional tools and materials.

In terms of networking system, opportunities to connect in a network within the virtual world have important connotations for all stages of teaching. The community of educators and teachers will attain skills for inclusive research and development, have unaffected access to students' works, scholarly research, and/or direct access to teaching databases worldwide. On the other hand, students, whether at school or at home, will have access to images via internet connection by phone, computer, or tablet at any hour of the day.

4. Conclusions

The computer has become an extremely powerful tool both in terms of outcomes and student learning as well as in terms of outcomes and teacher learning. It offers a new window into some previously unknown learning processes. The integration of computer technology into art education eliminates unhelpful and disapproving typecasts about art and offers a chance for art to take its well-deserved place in education facilities of all levels as a key foundation, which will ameliorate the level of art curricula and the skills of art teachers. Moreover, use of computer will be increased among people in the world of art and will also improve not only in art schools and universities, but also in homes and other art institutions, such as museums, cultural centers, exhibitions, etc.

In education, the use of technology as a spotlight for improving the teaching of thinking and learning processes, as well as the development of cognitive skills, is extremely valuable. Computer-assisted artwork can foster a learning atmosphere

that maintains communication and collaboration among students and can also be turned into an interactive learning environment. On the other hand, art students have many benefits from interacting with the computer. For this reason, the focus should be on students and forms of support for the efficient use of the computer in enhancing the quality of learning and art learning objectives. As for art teachers, they should be better trained in the use of technology, as they are responsible for educating and increasing the quality of the teaching process in the subject of art.

Art teachers need to understand the significance of employing computers as complementary educational instruments and means, so that the computer does not become a substitute for the traditional forms of art and teaching of art. Computer and art should be used in combination to improve the quality of art instruction and students' level of knowledge assimilation. Also, both students and teachers should be aware of the goals of using computer and its accessories in art classes and clearly understand the objectives and competencies of the art curriculum.

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